

**Restriction of sponges to an atoll lagoon as a result of
reduced environmental quality**

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Abstract

1 Heavy disturbance often leads to a change in environmental conditions and the
2 associated biota. Palmyra Atoll in the central Pacific was subject to major military
3 modifications across its lagoon system and islets during WWII. While the surrounding
4 reef is near-pristine and characterised by an abundance of top predators and high coral
5 cover, the dominant fauna in the disturbed lagoons are sponges. In this study we
6 quantified the physical and biological factors driving sponge distribution patterns to
7 determine the potential for the sponges in the lagoon at Palmyra to invade the
8 surrounding reef systems. Sponge cover was quantified at 11 sites across the 4
9 partially isolated lagoons at Palmyra along with a corresponding suite of biotic and
10 abiotic variables. Significant differences in sponge assemblages were found between
11 all but two sites. Ranked abundances indicated the dominance of an endemic
12 Hawaiian species; *Iotrochota protea*, across the lagoons and two known non-
13 indigenous species: *Haliclona (Sigmadocia) caerulea* and *Gelliodes fibrosa*. These
14 three species each had distinct relationships with biotic and abiotic factors. Overall,
15 40% and 80% of the variability in sponge assemblages and mean sponge cover across
16 sites was explained, respectively. The key factors structuring total sponge cover in the
17 lagoons were turbidity, variability in water flow and percentage hard substrate.
18 Substrate angle, abundance of human debris and variability in chlorophyll-*a* were the
19 top three variables for the variability in sponge assemblages, but no single factor
20 explained more than 10% of the variability. Our findings suggest that the lagoon
21 sponges at Palmyra are more than likely restricted to the lagoons and therefore
22 unlikely to spread to the reefs unless there is a dramatic decline in environmental
23 quality.

24

Keywords: Porifera, sponge assemblages, multivariate statistics, environmental associations, modifications, military, lagoon, coral reef, non-indigenous, introduced, Northern Line Islands

Introduction

25 Sponges are often understudied and overlooked but perform important
26 functional roles in coral reef ecosystems (Bell, 2008; Wulff, 2001) including spatial
27 competition, erosion and consolidation of reefs (Rützler, 1975; Wulff, 1984), benthopelagic coupling (Lesser, 2006), nutrient recycling (Diaz and Ward, 1997), facilitating
28 primary production through symbiosis (Wilkinson, 1983) and providing microhabitats
29 and food sources for other organisms (Wulff, 1994). Consequently, where sponges are
30 in high enough densities they can have considerable impacts on an aquatic ecosystem
31 (e.g. Peterson et al., 2006). Therefore, understanding what factors drive sponge
32 distributions is important to ascertain for the future management of any ecosystem.
33

34 Sponge distribution patterns and abundance vary spatially depending on a
35 number of environmental and biological factors, such as depth (Knapp and Bell,
36 2010), water flow (Bell and Barnes, 2003), sedimentation (Carballo, 2006; de Voogd
37 and Cleary, 2007), predation (Dunlap and Pawlik, 1996) salinity (Roberts et al., 2006)
38 nutrient levels (Wilkinson and Cheshire, 1989), light levels (Cheshire and Wilkinson,
39 1991), substrate type and angle (Bell and Barnes, 2000a, b; Powell et al., 2010),
40 turbidity (Zea, 1994), and larval dispersal and recruitment (Maldonado and Young,
41 1996).

42 In general there is a paucity of studies which have examined sponge
43 assemblage diversity and abundance in the tropical Pacific (e.g. Bell and Smith, 2004;
44 Carballo and Nava, 2007; de Voogd et al., 2006; Wilkinson and Cheshire, 1988) in
45 particular the Central Pacific (e.g. Bell and Carballo, 2008; Knapp and Bell, 2010)
46 with little known about the environmental parameters shaping the sponge assemblages
47 in these coral reef ecosystems (de Voogd and Cleary, 2007).

48 Coral reefs globally are highly diverse ecosystems providing numerous
49 ecological and economic benefits (Moberg and Folke, 1999). Despite their
50 importance, coral reefs are under major anthropogenic pressure (Hoegh-Guldberg,
51 2011; Richmond, 1993) to the extent that no reefs can now be considered pristine
52 (Jackson, 2003). Alterations and modifications to marine environments, such as coral
53 reefs, are likely to change the structure and function of these ecosystems by
54 extirpating species, reducing light levels and available substrate and increasing
55 sediment loading and nutrient pollution (Cranfield et al., 2004; Fabricius, 2005;
56 Rogers, 1990). When such disturbances are extreme, complex ecosystems can be
57 rapidly transformed to simple ones and become characterised by reduced diversity
58 (Rapport and Whitford, 1999). Modifications and the removal of native fauna also
59 make habitats more susceptible to invasions by non-indigenous species (NIS)
60 (Mooney and Cleland, 2001), as well as inadvertently creating conditions and
61 providing substrate that are preferential to the NIS over the existing biota (Byers,
62 2002; Tyrrell and Byers, 2007).

63 Studying near-pristine reef systems is important, as it allows us to examine
64 how coral reefs function in the absence of major direct human impacts. Palmyra Atoll,
65 situated 1,930 km south of the Hawaiian archipelago, is considered a near-pristine site
66 and represents a biodiversity hotspot in the Central Pacific (Maragos and Williams,
67 2011). Palmyra is; however, an interesting Atoll system in that the outer reefs are
68 characterized by a high cover of calcifying organisms and abundant predatory fish
69 (Sandin et al., 2008), while the prominent benthic fauna in the lagoons, where
70 extensive habitat modifications occurred, are sponges (Bell & Carballo, 2008). The
71 lagoons were subject to a number of military modifications during WWII (Dawson,
72 1959). The extensive dredging and construction at Palmyra during this time removed

73 endemic fauna, such as corals from the lagoons (Anon., 1947), and altered the
74 environmental conditions by stemming the flow of water between lagoons (Collen,
75 2009; Dawson, 1959; Maragos, 1993).

76 It has been postulated, because of the shape of the Atoll, that the pre-war
77 lagoon at Palmyra might have been more similar to that of Millennium Atoll's
78 lagoons (pers comms Jim Maragos), which is dominated by *Acropora* spp. but also
79 characterised by high crustose coralline algae cover, turfing algae and the giant clam
80 *Tridacna maxima* (Barott et al., 2010). A large number of old *T.maxima* shells remain
81 in Palmyra's lagoon also supporting this suggestion. The military modifications at
82 Palmyra therefore most likely reduced species diversity, made the lagoon system
83 more vulnerable to NIS and led to the current environmental conditions which
84 harbour sponges as the dominant benthic fauna. Two non-indigenous sponge species
85 have already been reported in the lagoons (Knapp et al., 2011) but it is unknown how
86 many more have been introduced or whether any invaders have the potential to extend
87 onto the adjacent near-pristine reef. Of particular concern at Palmyra is spatial
88 competition between sponges and native fauna and the potential impact the sponges
89 may have on the lagoonal waters (e.g. nutrient removal), which flow predominantly in
90 a westward direction out onto the surrounding near-pristine reef (Gardner et al.,
91 2011). Currently, the sponge assemblages in the lagoons and the reefs at Palmyra also
92 share no common species (Knapp unpub. data) suggesting abiotic and biotic factors
93 might be maintaining the sponges in the lagoons.

94 The aims of this research were therefore to: 1) identify the sponge species
95 distribution patterns across the lagoons and the principal indicator species driving
96 them; 2) ascertain what variables are driving the sponge assemblages, overall sponge
97 percentage cover and abundance of notable species (known non-indigenous species

98 and dominant species); and 3) assess the potential for the lagoon sponges to extend on
99 to the adjacent near pristine reef.

Methods

100 Study Site

101 Palmyra Atoll is a U.S. National Wildlife Refuge, part of the Pacific Remote
102 Island Areas (PRIAs), as well as the Pacific Remote Islands Marine National
103 Monument (proclamation 8336) established in 2009. The Atoll is approximately 6 km
104 long and made up of 50 islets covering an area of approximately 2.8 km² with 4
105 partially isolated lagoons and the surrounding coral reef system encompassing 62.8
106 km². Palmyra was privately owned until December 2000 but is now co-owned by The
107 Nature Conservancy (TNC) and United States Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS).

108 The U.S. military modifications during WWII were extensive and included
109 dredging the lagoons to deepen them for boats, using the spoil to build up and connect
110 the islets, building large iron docks and wharfs and excavating a channel through the
111 western reef terrace to allow boat access (Dawson, 1959; Maragos, 1993) (Fig. 1).
112 The military presence is still clearly visible today with iron structures littered around
113 the lagoons, in particular the Ripple Wharf in the Western Lagoon, which is still used
114 to dock large boats and the built-up north-south causeway constructed between the
115 Eastern and Central Lagoons (Fig. 1). The north-south causeway once completely
116 blocked the flow of water between the lagoons but has now breached in several places
117 returning some movement between the lagoons.

118 Sponge assemblage surveys

119 Between June to November 2008 sponge assemblage surveys were conducted
120 across the 4 lagoons at 11 sites at depths between 5-8 m. The site selection criterion

121 was based on achieving representative sampling across the lagoons. At each site 10 x
122 1 m² quadrats (divided into 20 x 20 cm sub-sections) were haphazardly placed on
123 boulder patches on the substrate. In total, 110 m² of substrate was surveyed across the
124 lagoons at Palmyra. These observations focused on sponges found on the surface of
125 the boulders rather than those underneath boulders. Excavating (bioeroding) species
126 were not included because accurate estimates of area cover were not possible. Within
127 each quadrat sub-section we estimated percentage cover of each species and the total
128 available substrate. If a sponge extended beyond the quadrat only the area in the sub-
129 section was estimated and if a sponge extended into an adjacent sub-section the area
130 cover was estimated independently in each. All data was adjusted to the percentage of
131 available substrate to enable direct comparisons between sites by accounting for the
132 variability in overall boulder densities.

133 **Sponge collections and identifications**

134 Sponge samples during our baseline surveys were collected from all
135 unidentified species inside and outside of the quadrats. Where possible, three samples
136 of each species were collected and stored in >95% ethanol. All samples were
137 identified by examining phenotypic characteristics and spicule preparations and
138 sections.

139 **Biotic and abiotic variables**

140 A suite of variables were collected at each site at depths of 5-8 m from 2008 to
141 2010. Despite the length of time over which the environmental parameters were
142 accumulated, individual variables were collected simultaneously to ensure
143 comparability across sites.

144 Temperature (°C) data were collected using pendant HOBO[®] temperature data
145 loggers (accuracy of ± 0.54°C) (www.onsetcomp.com). Each logger was set to record

146 every 2 minutes between June-July 2010. RBR[®] XR-420 data loggers ([www.rbr-](http://www.rbr-global.com)
147 [global.com](http://www.rbr-global.com)), recording every minute between June-November 2008 and June-July
148 2010, measured salinity, turbidity (as a proxy for sediment load), chlorophyll-*a* and
149 additional temperature data. Chlorophyll-*a* is used here as an estimate of food
150 availability because it is a measure of the available phytoplankton in the water and
151 correlates positively with bacteria levels (Cole et al., 1988), which are major food
152 sources for sponges (Pile et al., 1996; Reiswig, 1971, 1975). Unfortunately, the
153 remote nature of Palmyra Atoll made it impossible to collect water samples for
154 complete food particle analysis (e.g. with flow cytometry).

155 Water flow was recorded every 10 seconds using a Valeport[®] Model 106
156 Current Meter (www.valeport.co.uk) deployed between June-November 2008 and
157 June-July 2010.

158 Percentage organic matter (%) (PCOM) and total particulate matter ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) (TPM) in settled sediment was measured 2-5 times between June-November 2008
159 and 2009 using PVC sediment traps (See Bloesch, 1994). Upon collection, each trap
160 contents was filtered through grade 114 wet strengthened Whatman[®] filter papers and
161 put into a muffle furnace at 60°C and left to dry until it reached a constant weight.
162 The dry weight and number of days the trap remained in the water was used to
163 calculate TPM. The samples were then placed into a muffle furnace at 500°C for 24
164 hours to obtain the ash-free dry weight. The amount of weight loss after combustion
165 was used to calculate the particulate organic matter ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) (POM). PCOM,
166 which was calculated as $\text{POM}/\text{TPM} \times 100$ (Craft et al., 1991).

168 The percentage algal cover, anthropogenic debris and hard and soft substrate
169 (boulders and sand) were quantified using 10 x 1m² photoquadrats taken at each site.
170 Estimates of benthic cover were collected independently from the sponge cover

171 surveys because boulders were targeted for this portion of the survey and would give
172 a biased representation for each site. Anthropogenic debris included all obvious
173 anthropogenic structures or waste including metal cables, parts from vehicles and
174 other such material. In order to obtain random sampling, when characterising the
175 habitats a 30 m transect was laid at 5-8 m and a 1 m² quadrat placed on either side of
176 the transect at 5 m intervals (n = 10) from 25 m to 5 m. By not placing the quadrats at
177 either 0 m or 30 m, we removed the likelihood of observer bias when laying the
178 transect tape. Substrate percentage cover values were calculated using Coral Point
179 Count with excel extensions (CPCe) software (Kohler and Gill, 2006). One hundred
180 randomly assigned points were placed over each 1 m², equalling 1000 points per site,
181 and 11,000 points across the Atoll covering a total of 110 m².

182 Grain size analysis of the sediment was examined by collecting *in situ* bulk
183 sediment samples from the beginning and end of the quadrat transects. Each sample
184 was then separated using standard brass sieves (USA Standard Testing Sieve- ASTM.
185 E-11 specifications) into the fractions: rubble (> 2.8 mm), coarse sand (500 µm – 2.8
186 mm), medium sand (250 – 500 µm), fine sand (63 – 250 µm) and silt/clay (< 63 µm)
187 in accordance with the Wentworth scale (Folk, 1974). The largest grain size class
188 (>2.8mm) was subsequently discarded because there is no upper size limit and would
189 therefore skew the results. The four remaining fractions were poured into and drained
190 through pre-weighed grade 114 wet strengthened Whatman® filter papers and dried in
191 an incubator for 2 days at 60°C. The samples were then allowed to cool to room
192 temperature and weighed. The samples were then dried for additional 24 h periods
193 until a constant weight was achieved. Proportions (%) for each size class were
194 calculated as 100/total weight x class weight. The four size classes were then reduced
195 into two: coarse to medium sand (250 µm – 2.8 mm) and fine sand to silt (< 63 µm –

196 250 μm). The final variable included in the model was substrate slope /angle, which
197 was categorical and sites were either classed as sloping (1) $\approx 40\text{-}50^\circ$ or horizontal (2)
198 $\approx 0^\circ$.

199 **Statistical analyses**

200 *Diversity indices*

201 Across sites, we characterised and compared sponge assemblages using a
202 number of diversity indices: number of species (S); Hill's numbers N1 and N2 and the
203 modified Hill's ratio (N21'). Hill's numbers N1 and N2 indicate the influence of rare
204 and dominant species (respectively) and Hill's ratio examines species equitability
205 (evenness) without any dependency on the number of species (Rogers et al., 1999).

206 *Multivariate analyses*

207 All assemblage data, prior to the analyses, were dispersion weighted (based on
208 1000 permutations), which differentially weights species depending on their observed
209 variability between samples (Clarke et al., 2006a) and is suitable for species prone to
210 spatial clustering such as sponges. Similarity matrices were based on zero-adjusted
211 Bray-Curtis coefficients and account for denuded data (Clarke et al., 2006b), which
212 was characteristic of a number of sites.

213 A permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) (based on
214 9999 permutations) (Anderson, 2001; Clarke et al., 2006b) and pairwise *post hoc* tests
215 were used to examine differences in sponge cover at two separate factor levels; lagoon
216 (West, Central, Eastern and Turtle pool) and site (all 11 sites) (See Fig 1). To
217 visualise the PERMANOVA results, non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (nMDS)
218 and canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) plots (using 9999
219 permutations), with allocation success values, were examined (Anderson and Willis,
220 2003). Allocation success values (%) were calculated using the leave-one-out

221 procedure of the CAP analysis (Anderson and Willis, 2003) and indicated the relative
222 distinctness between assemblages. Allocation values greater than 25% (for the 4
223 lagoons) and 9.09% (for the 11 sites) were considered to indicate more distinct
224 assemblages than those expected by chance alone. Indicator species, those which most
225 characterise a site (Dufrêne and Legendre, 1997) and responsible for the observed
226 differences between assemblage patterns in the CAP plot were examined by
227 calculating Pearson's product-moment correlations of canonical ordinations axes with
228 the original sponge percentage cover data (Anderson, 2004). Those species identified
229 as indicator species (defined as ≥ 0.5 in this study) were graphically displayed as
230 vectors on a bi-plot.

231 Ranked species abundances were calculated by separately totalling sponge
232 cover data per species and ranking them from the most to the least abundant,
233 indicating how common or rare a sponge species ranked relative to all other sponges
234 across the lagoons.

235 *Sponge assemblage environmental associations*

236 Analysis and modeling of the univariate and multivariate sponge data with the
237 environmental, biological and categorical predictor variables were conducted using a
238 distance-based linear model (DistLM) (McArdle and Anderson, 2001). Notable
239 species were also examined; *Iotrochota protea*, *Haliclona (Sigmadocia) caerulea* and
240 *Gelliodes fibrosa*. *H. caerulea* and *G. fibrosa* are two confirmed non-indigenous
241 species introduced to Palmyra (Knapp et al., 2011) and Hawaii (DeFelice et al.,
242 2001), from the Caribbean and the Philippines, respectively. *Iotrochota protea* (de
243 Laubenfels, 1950), the dominant species, is native to Hawaii, but it is unknown
244 whether it was found on Palmyra prior to military occupation. From here on
245 *Haliclona (Sigmadocia) caerulea* will be referred to in the text as *Haliclona caerulea*.

246 The DistLM routine conducts a multivariate multiple regression to quantitatively
247 explain how much variation in the sponge assemblage data can be explained by the
248 biotic and abiotic variables. A total of twenty one environmental and biological
249 variables were initially measured (**Table 3**), seven of which were one standard
250 deviation (+1SD) values, which represent the variability of the factor at an individual
251 site. To examine colineation between the variables we examined draftsman plots and
252 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) ordinations. Inter-correlation values > 0.75
253 (lower than the recommended 0.95 cut-off ([Anderson et al., 2008](#))) between two
254 variables were considered for removal but first examined further using PCA plots.
255 Those factors removed from the model lay in the same direction and length as the
256 other colineating variable in the PCA plots and were therefore redundant as variables.
257 Fine sand/silt and coarse-medium sand had an inter-correlation value of 1.0, as
258 expected with samples that are proportional to each other. Therefore only fine
259 sand/silt was included in the model. Information on sites characterised by more coarse
260 material is not lost from the model, they simply lie on the negative end of the grain
261 size scale. Temperature also colineated with turbidity (0.81); however further
262 examination of the PCA plots revealed that temperature fell out in the opposite
263 direction to turbidity and was therefore left in the model because it was characteristic
264 of different sites. The following variables were removed from the final model: coarse
265 /medium sediment, total particulate matter (TPM), TPM (+1SD), turbidity (+1SD),
266 chlorophyll-a, and water flow, resulting in the inclusion of fifteen predictor variables
267 into the DisLM model. The routine was run using the 'best' selection procedure,
268 based on 9999 permutations of the residuals under the reduced model. The model
269 selection criteria was determined using Akaike's information criterion ([Akaike, 1973](#))
270 with a second-order bias correction applied (AICc) ([Burnham and Anderson, 2002](#)).

271 The most parsimonious model with the lowest AICc value was selected. In this study,
272 each site (**Fig 1**), consisting of 10 x 1m² quadrats, was considered an independent
273 observation with independent variables collected for each of the 11 locations.
274 Distance-based redundancy analyses (dbRDA) were used to visualise and interpret the
275 optimal models (McArdle and Anderson, 2001). Sites are displayed by a group
276 centroid, the closer two centroids are the more similar the sponge assemblages are
277 between those two sites. The length and direction of each vector line indicates the
278 strength and sign (+ve or -ve) of the relationship between the predictor variables and
279 the sites. Sites in the opposite direction of the line are negative or lower values of the
280 variable. All analyses were conducted using PRIMER v6 (Clarke and Gorley, 2006)
281 and the PERMANOVA+ add-on package (Anderson et al., 2008).

Results

282 A total of 36 sponge species were recorded across the lagoons at Palmyra
283 Atoll (**Table 1**), of which 24 were recorded during the baseline surveys in 2008 and
284 the remainder were rare species and observed outside of the quadrats, found deeper
285 than 8 m or were excluded because they were excavating species. A total of 13
286 genera, 16 families and 7 orders of sponges were observed in the lagoons. Excluding
287 excavating species, 4 morphological groups were represented in the lagoon;
288 encrusting, cushion, massive and digitate. The Ripple wharf in the Western lagoon
289 had the lowest number of species (S= 8) and the Cut in the Central lagoon and Quail
290 in the Eastern lagoon the highest (S= 17), with an overall average of 15 (\pm 2.6) sponge
291 species per site (**Fig 2b**). Both Hill numbers N1 and N2 indicated similar patterns
292 across sites with the highest measure of diversity and evenness (**Fig 2d**) found at the

293 Dolphins (N1 and N2) and the Ripple wharf (N21'), respectively, and the lowest at
294 Strawn for all indices.

295 Mean sponge cover fluctuated between sites across the lagoons (**Fig. 3a**) and ranged
296 from 15.8% (± 5.7) at Turtle Pool, in the far Eastern lagoon, to 36.2% (± 14.7) at
297 Strawn, in the Western lagoon (**Fig 1**), with an overall mean of 27.0% (± 11.6).
298 Significant differences in sponge cover occurred between sites (Pseudo- $F_{10, 109} =$
299 7.1439, $p = <0.001$). Further pair-wise revealed that all sites were significantly
300 different from each other except for Strawn and Paradise, in the Western lagoon ($t =$
301 1.26, $p = 0.1439$). Significant differences were also found between all four lagoons
302 (Pseudo- $F_{3, 109} = 9.2053$, $p = <0.001$). The CAP output also identified significant
303 differences in sponge assemblages between sites and lagoons (**Fig 3 and Table 2**).
304 Each site and lagoon had higher allocation success values than would be expected by
305 chance alone.

306 **Ranked and indicator species**

307 Out of 24 species identified within the survey quadrats three were
308 characteristic of different sites (**Fig 3**); *Dysidea* sp 1 (B) for the Dolphins in the
309 Western lagoon; Chondropsidae sp. (T) for the Central and Eastern lagoons and
310 *Hymeniacidon* sp.1 (H) for the Central lagoon.

311 The ranked abundances (**Fig 4**) formed a hyperbola-shaped curve indicating
312 the dominance of a few common species and a large number of 'rare' species in the
313 Palmyra system, essentially resulting in low evenness. The three species with the
314 highest cover across all the lagoons were predominantly different to the indicator
315 species, which is to be expected because when a species is widespread it is less likely
316 to be characteristic of one or a few sites. The Chondropsidae sp. was both an indicator
317 species and had the second highest cover across all the lagoons. *Iotrochota protea* had

318 the highest percentage mean cover across all lagoons except the Eastern lagoon (Fig
319 4), with the greatest mean ($14.17\% \pm 8.2$) in the Western lagoon.

320 **Drivers of notable species**

321 The three notable species were all correlated with different environmental
322 variables. Temperature explained 25.3 % of the variability for *Haliclona caerulea*,
323 showing a weak negative relationship, with warmer sites having lower cover.
324 *Haliclona caerulea* was most abundant in the Western lagoon at Strawn and the
325 Dolphins, and at Turtle Pool (the far Eastern lagoon). Both Turtle Pool and the
326 Dolphins had the lowest mean temperatures ($27.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.4$ and $28.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.7$)
327 whereas Strawn had the highest overall cover of all sponges, which might explain the
328 cover of *H. caerulea* here. At those sites where *Gelliodes fibrosa* was recorded, cover
329 was positively correlated with Percentage Organic Matter (PCOM), which explained
330 29.0% of the variability. The highest PCOM and *G. fibrosa* cover was at Paradise
331 (Western lagoon) with 15.3 % and 1.15 % respectively. The Ripple wharf and Strawn
332 (Western lagoon) had the lowest cover of *G. fibrosa* (0.06 and 0.27 %, respectively)
333 along with the lowest levels of PCOM (13.7 and 11.1 %, respectively). The
334 abundance of *Iotrochota protea*, the species with the highest cover across the majority
335 of the lagoons, was correlated with substrate angle and variability in chlorophyll-a,
336 which explained 28.0% and 31.4% of the variability, respectively. Sloped sites, with
337 the exception of Eastern Island had the highest cover of *I. protea* ranging from 7.3 %
338 to 20.61%. The two horizontal sites; Central Eastern, the Dolphins, and Eastern Island
339 had the lowest cover (3.97, 4.63 and 3.92 %, respectively). Variability in Chlorophyll-
340 *a* had a weak negative relationship with *I. protea* abundance with the lowest cover and
341 highest standard deviation in chlorophyll-*a* levels (1.30% and $0.33\text{ }\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$) both at the
342 Eastern Island site in the Eastern lagoon.

343 **Drivers of sponge cover**

344 Out of fifteen variables (See **Table 3**), a total of 80.4% of the variability in
345 overall sponge cover between sites was explained by 3 factors; turbidity (39.8 %),
346 flow rate variability (1SD) (21.8 %) and % hard substrate (18.8 %). Turbidity had an
347 overall negative relationship with sponge area cover, with Turtle Pool having the
348 highest turbidity ($5.97 \text{ STU} \pm 2.05$) and lowest sponge cover (15.8 %) (See **Table 3**).
349 Variability in water flow was highest at Sand Island ($0.0422 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$) (Western
350 lagoon) and the Cut ($0.0363 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$) (Central lagoon) and the lowest at Eastern
351 Island ($0.0031 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$) (Eastern lagoon) with the remaining sites between 0.0099
352 and $0.0185 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Percentage hard substrate was lowest at the Ripple wharf (8.5
353 %) in the Western lagoon, which is also the location with the highest percentage cover
354 of anthropogenic debris (12.0%) (See **Table 3**) and the most likely reason for this low
355 hard substrate cover. Turtle Pool has the second highest hard substrate cover (30.2 %),
356 but the lowest area cover of sponges (15.8 %).

357 **Drivers of sponge assemblages**

358 Variability in sponge assemblages between sites (**Fig. 5**) primarily correlated
359 with substrate angle, chlorophyll-*a* variability and the percentage cover of
360 anthropogenic debris, explaining 7.1 %, 6.1 % and 5.5 % of the variability,
361 respectively. The total amount of variability explained by all significant
362 environmental and biological factors was 41.1 %, with the top 3 contributing
363 approximately half (18.7 %) of the variability when combined. Substrate angle was
364 negatively correlated with the Dolphins, one of the two horizontal sites.
365 Anthropogenic debris was positively correlated with the Ripple Wharf, Sand Island
366 and the Dolphins, all in the Western lagoon. The Ripple wharf had the highest
367 anthropogenic debris (12.0 %), followed by the Dolphins (0.8 %). Sand Island has no

368 visible anthropogenic debris; however, it is an artificial island, a product of the
369 excavation spoils from the channel and therefore an artefact of the military activities.
370 Variability in Chlorophyll-*a* was positively correlated with Eastern Island, Central
371 Eastern (Eastern lagoon) and the Cut (Central lagoon) which had a mean standard
372 deviation of 0.23 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$, and negatively correlated with the majority of Western lagoon
373 sites, which had a mean variability of 0.18 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$.

Discussion

374 Sponges are an important component of marine ecosystems (Bell, 2008;
375 Wulff, 2001) and understanding the factors responsible for their diversity and
376 assemblage structure is important for understanding overall reef function. At Palmyra
377 Atoll in the remote central Pacific, we found that turbidity, variability in water flow
378 and percentage hard substrate together explained a total of 80.4% of the variability in
379 overall sponge cover between sites. While only 40% of the variability in sponge
380 assemblage structure was explained by nine variables, no single variable explained
381 more than 8% of the variation. Of the 24 species observed in the quadrats, three were
382 characteristic of groups of sites. *Iotrochota protea*, a Hawaiian endemic and possibly
383 introduced species to Palmyra (given that natural dispersal seems unlikely), had the
384 greatest cover across all lagoons with the highest overall mean cover in the Western
385 lagoon. The notable species; *Haliclona caerulea* and *Gelliodes fibrosa* and *Iotrochota*
386 *protea*, each had different variables when modelled separately. This increased
387 understanding of the distribution, abundance and environmental relationships of
388 sponge assemblages suggests that the sponge species within the lagoons are most
389 likely restricted to this environment and are unlikely to spread to the outer reefs. In

390 addition, some of the sponge species might be useful indicators for observing a
391 decline in environmental quality at Palmyra's backreef sites.

392 **Sponge species at Palmyra Atoll**

393 There is a paucity of ecological research on sponge assemblages from Pacific
394 islands, particularly in the Central region, south of Hawaii. Previous studies have
395 shown the number of species reported from Pacific islands ranges between 8 and 60
396 (Bergquist, 1965; Chiriboga, 2011; de Laubenfels, 1951, 1954; Soest et al., 2011).
397 Palmyra Atoll has 36 sponge species within the lagoons (**Table 1**) and approximately
398 14 more on the reefs (Knapp unpub. data), totalling 50 species identified thus far,
399 which is therefore similar to other Pacific islands, but much lower than other tropical
400 areas such as Indonesia and Australia (See Bell, 2007).

401 The number of species per site at Palmyra was similar across the lagoons with
402 the exception of the man-made Ripple wharf in the Western lagoon, which had the
403 lowest number of species. The low number of species at this site is most likely due to
404 the high percentage of anthropogenic construction and debris resulting in low
405 available hard substrate for sponges to inhabit, also some sponge species may not
406 settle on artificial substrate because these surfaces are smoother (Knott et al., 2004).
407 The Western lagoon at Palmyra is the proposed location for all the non-indigenous
408 introductions (Knapp et al., 2011) and in general had low diversity with only a few
409 species dominating at Strawn and Paradise in particular. *Iotrochota protea* accounted,
410 on average, for half of the total sponge cover for all of the Western lagoon sites. The
411 Dolphins was the only exception, which was distinctly different to all other sites
412 because it had a greater number of rare species and was even characterised by one of
413 these rarer individuals: *Dysidea* sp.1. The high number of rare species at the Dolphins

414 is possibly because it was the location of a WWII boat dock resulting in high exposure
415 to introduced species via fouling and ballast water.

416 **Notable sponge species in the lagoons**

417 It is currently unknown how many of the sponge species are native to Palmyra.
418 Across all lagoons the native Hawaiian species; *I. protea*, had the highest cover and
419 was found at all sites. Little is known about *Iotrochota protea* except that it is found
420 on sandy or rubble substrates in sheltered bays (Hoover, 2006) and characterised by
421 staining the skin dark purple when touched. This lack of knowledge is of concern
422 considering that *I. protea* is a potential NIS (since most sponge species have very poor
423 dispersal ability and it seems unlikely natural colonisation would have occurred) and
424 covers approximately 13% of the boulders at the majority of sites, which on average is
425 half of the total sponge cover. However, considering *I. protea* is generally associated
426 with low current conditions (Hoover, 2006) this species is potentially prevented from
427 dispersing to the backreefs because of the higher water flow rates here.

428 The environmental parameters driving sponge distribution patterns in the
429 lagoons at Palmyra were distinct between sponge species. *Iotrochota protea* was
430 negatively correlated with variability in chlorophyll-*a* and positively correlated with
431 inclined surfaces over horizontal ones. A negative correlation with variability in
432 chlorophyll-*a* indicates that those sites with higher sponge cover have more stable
433 food sources. Substrate inclination has also long been identified as influencing the
434 distribution of sponges because of the different physical characteristics such as
435 sedimentation, light, and water flow correlated with an inclined versus horizontal
436 substrata (Bell and Barnes, 2000b; Bell and Smith, 2004; Wilkinson and Evans,
437 1989). However, despite the mechanisms for *I. protea* to inhabit high sediment sites in

438 the lagoon, cover was higher on inclined sites compared to horizontal ones where
439 sediment settlement will be lower.

440 *Haliclona caerulea* was negatively correlated with temperature, with a higher
441 percentage cover found in colder waters and was virtually absent at sites with
442 temperatures over 29°C. Temperature was also negatively correlated with turbidity.
443 *Haliclona caerulea* in this study had higher cover in the cooler more turbid sites and
444 in other localities round the world is only found in low water flow and highly turbid
445 conditions (DeFelice et al., 2001). Therefore we predict that *H. caerulea* would only
446 potentially extend onto the backreef if environmental conditions declined resulting in
447 higher turbidity and cooler temperatures.

448 *Gelliodes fibrosa* was positively correlated with the percentage of organic
449 matter (PCOM) in the sediment, which is a potential indicator of food availability for
450 sponges (Reiswig, 1971) as it correlates positively with bacterial production (Cole et
451 al., 1988). A large number of the encrusting species at Palmyra, including *I. protea*,
452 have a fine sediment layer on the surface of the sponges (Fig 6) excluding the oscular
453 and, depending on the species, surface veins. Both particulate and dissolved organic
454 matter in sediments are higher than in the water column, therefore the lagoon sponges,
455 and possible symbionts, have the potential to use this as a nutritional resource (Ilan
456 and Abelson, 1995). Backreef values of PCOM (Williams et al., 2011) are also 4-5
457 times lower than in the lagoon indicating that *G. fibrosa* distributions are likely
458 dictated by food availability, which are potentially too low on the backreef for this
459 species to survive.

460 **Drivers of sponge cover and assemblages**

461 The sponge assemblages in the lagoons at Palmyra were significantly
462 associated with nine biotic and abiotic variables. However, not one of the variables

463 accounted for more than 8 % of the variability and therefore individually had
464 relatively low ecological significance, with the top 3 variables only explaining 18.67
465 % of the total variation. The top two variables were the same as the two variables for
466 *I. protea* perhaps suggesting that this species is having a large influence on the sponge
467 assemblages across the lagoons (despite dispersion weighting). The third variable;
468 anthropogenic debris, suggests that the assemblages on the boulders at the Ripple
469 Wharf differed significantly because of the adjacent anthropogenic debris.

470 For overall sponge cover, the top 3 variables were turbidity, variability in
471 water flow and percentage hard substrate, which explained 80.35 % of the variability
472 between sites. The current environmental conditions in the lagoons at Palmyra are that
473 of low water flow and high sedimentation with the benthos characterised by
474 fine/coarse sediment and boulders. Substrate availability is low in the lagoon;
475 boulders (< 0.5 m²) are common but larger areas of hard surface are rare. Not
476 surprisingly therefore we found percentage hard substrate had a weak positive
477 correlation with sponge cover. We found water flow was also positively correlated
478 with sponge cover between sites at Palmyra, with Sand Island in the Western lagoon
479 and the Cut in the Central lagoon, situated nearest to access channels, having the
480 highest water flow levels along with the greatest percentage cover of sponge. Water
481 flow is important for facultatively-active suspension feeders, like sponges, because
482 passage into and through the sponge can be induced by ambient waters (Vogel, 1977),
483 which provides their food source. Therefore higher water flow supplies food to the
484 sponge more efficiently and increases food availability.

485 We also found a negative relationship between turbidity and sponge cover
486 possibly because high sediment can clog the delicate filtering apparatus of sponges
487 (Bell, 2004) as well as smother available hard substrate for larvae to settle. Turtle

488 Pool, in the far east, had the lowest sponge cover and was also correlated with the
489 highest turbidity levels whilst Quail with higher than average cover had the lowest
490 turbidity levels. Bell and Smith (2004) noted sponge percentage cover was greater
491 with higher sedimentation levels. Nevertheless, Bell and Smith's study compared two
492 coral reef locations, which more than likely experience greater water flow and lower
493 sediment loading than the most turbid site in the lagoons at Palmyra: Turtle Pool.
494 Turtle Pool had nearly 3 times higher turbidity levels than the next turbid site
495 (Paradise, in the Western lagoon). Therefore there is a relatively large range of
496 turbidity levels for which we have no sponge assemblage information (2-5 STU). The
497 high turbidity levels at Turtle Pool do however provide an insight into how sponge
498 cover might be affected by large increases in sedimentation, for example if the North-
499 South military causeway (**Fig 2**) was removed as discussed by Williams et al. (2011).
500 If turbidity increases substantially in the lagoons there is possibility that not only coral
501 species will be affected, but the sponges as well. Despite the unknown origin of the
502 sponges in the lagoon, their highly efficient water filtering capabilities might be
503 having a positive influence in returning the lagoons to their pre-war state. For
504 example, Peterson (2006) found that sponges have the potential to control nuisance
505 phytoplankton blooms in the Florida keys.

506 The distribution of reef organisms can also be greatly affected by increases in
507 sedimentation because of the impact on larval settlement and survival (Connell et al.,
508 1997; Hodgson, 1990). Research on the factors controlling sponge larval settlement
509 and recruitment is limited. Water flow can, for some species, be positively associated
510 with juvenile survivorship and adult abundance (Maldonado and Young, 1996) and if
511 strong enough remove larval selection at settlement (Butman, 1987; Woodin, 1986).
512 The water flow rates in the lagoons at 5-8m is $<0.036 \text{ cm}^2\text{sec}^{-1}$ and sponge swimming

513 speeds have been recorded between 0.1-1 cm²sec⁻¹ (e.g. Bergquist et al., 1970;
514 Maldonado and Young, 1996), therefore theoretically the sponge larvae in the lagoons
515 at Palmyra could swim against the prevailing water flow to settle in more preferential
516 locations. Low temperatures, which we found had a negative relationship with
517 turbidity, can also inhibit larval dispersal by decreasing the swimming speed of the
518 larvae and shortening the free-swimming phase and inhibiting recruitment
519 (Maldonado and Young, 1996). We found that Turtle Pool along with having the
520 highest turbidity levels also has the lowest mean temperatures and sponge cover
521 (Table 3). Interestingly, we recorded both *H. caerulea* and *I. protea* at Turtle Pool,
522 which is located furthest from the Western lagoon, the suggested location for all the
523 introduced species (Knapp et al., 2011). Therefore, because these species have
524 managed to extend to the opposite side of the Atoll, against the prevailing westward
525 water flow (Gardner et al., 2011), it appears unlikely that the sponges will extend onto
526 the reef unless there is a decline in environmental quality there. To support this,
527 lagoon and reef species lists are also different, with no species common to both
528 environments (Knapp unpub. data). Furthermore fish predation was also examined as
529 this has been noted as a key driving factor of sponge distributions in the Caribbean
530 (Pawlik, 1998; Wulff, 2000). However, a preliminary fish predation experiment;
531 where seven lagoon sponge species were transplanted onto five backreef sites,
532 observed no predation (Knapp, unpub.) and is therefore an unlikely mechanism
533 maintaining the sponges off the reef at Palmyra.

534 Sponges at Palmyra, if driven by environmental conditions such as
535 temperature, water flow, turbidity and chlorophyll-a, might therefore be important
536 indicator species of any decline in water quality on the backreef. The inner south-
537 western backreef (a site known as Penguin spit) would be the proposed location to

538 monitor for the introduction of lagoon species to the reef as it already has the highest
539 densities of reef sponge species (Knapp pers. obs.) and the highest sedimentation
540 levels (Williams et al., 2011).

Conclusions

541 Overall sponge diversity at Palmyra is comparable to other Pacific islands and
542 atolls; however, it is still unknown how many species are native to the lagoons.
543 Species diversity, when examining Hills N1, was on average the lowest in the
544 Western lagoon, indicating that few species dominate these habitats. An exception to
545 this was a site known as the Dolphins (characterised by a series of man-made iron
546 structures), with the site having the highest species diversity atoll-wide. For all the
547 models examined (overall sponge cover, sponge assemblages and individual notable
548 species) the strongest environmental relationships are associated with
549 sedimentation/turbidity and food/habitat availability. The current distribution and
550 abundance patterns of sponges, particularly for *H. caerulea* and *I. protea*, suggests that
551 unless there is a dramatic decline in environmental quality on the reefs at Palmyra,
552 such as increased sedimentation and turbidity, the sponges will most likely remain
553 confined to the lagoons. Therefore, we propose that the appearance of lagoon sponge
554 species on Palmyra's reefs could act as an early warning to management of
555 environmental degradation.

556

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References

- 567 Akaike, H., 1973. Information theory as an extension of the maximum likelihood
568 principal, in: Petrov, B.N., Caski, F. (Eds.), Proceedings of the Second International
569 Symposium on Information Theory, Akademiai Kiado, Budapest.
- 570 Anderson, M.J., 2001. A new method for non-parametric multivariate analysis of
571 variance. *Austral Ecology* 26, 32-46.
- 572 Anderson, M.J., 2004. CAP: a FORTRAN computer program for canonical analysis
573 of principal coordinates. Department of Statistics, University of Auckland, New
574 Zealand.
- 575 Anderson, M.J., Gorley, R.N., Clarke, K.R., 2008. PERMANOVA+ for PRIMER:
576 Guide to Software and Statistical Methods. PRIMER-E Plymouth, UK.
- 577 Anderson, M.J., Willis, T.J., 2003. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates: a
578 useful method of constrained ordination for ecology. *Ecology* 84, 511-524.
- 579 Anon., 1947. Building the Navy's Bases in World War II; history of the bureau of
580 yards and docks and the civil engineer corps 1940-1946. U.S. Government Printing
581 Office, Washington.
- 582 Barott, K.L., Caselle, J.E., Dinsdale, E.A., Friedlander, A.M., Maragos, J.E., Obura,
583 D., Rohwer, F.L., Sandin, S.A., Smith, J.E., Zgliczynski, B., 2010. The Lagoon at
584 Caroline/Millennium Atoll, Republic of Kiribati: Natural History of a Nearly Pristine
585 Ecosystem. *PLoS ONE* 5, e10950.
- 586 Bell, J.J., 2004. Evidence for morphology-induced sediment settlement prevention on
587 the tubular sponge *Haliclona urceolus*. *Mar. Biol.* 146, 29-38.
- 588 Bell, J.J., 2007. The ecology of sponges in Lough Hyne Marine Nature Reserve
589 (south-west Ireland): Past, present and future perspectives. *J. Mar. Biol. Assoc. U.K.*
590 87, 1655-1668.
- 591 Bell, J.J., 2008. The functional roles of marine sponges. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 79,
592 341-353.

- 593 Bell, J.J., Barnes, D.K.A., 2000a. The distribution and prevalence of sponges in
594 relation to environmental gradients within a temperate sea lough: Inclined cliff
595 surfaces. *Divers. Distrib.* 6, 305-323.
- 596 Bell, J.J., Barnes, D.K.A., 2000b. The distribution and prevalence of sponges in
597 relation to environmental gradients within a temperate sea lough: Vertical cliff
598 surfaces. *Divers. Distrib.* 6, 283-303.
- 599 Bell, J.J., Barnes, D.K.A., 2003. Effect of Disturbance on Assemblages: An Example
600 Using Porifera. *Biological Bulletin* 205, 144-159.
- 601 Bell, J.J., Carballo, J.L., 2008. Patterns of sponge biodiversity and abundance across
602 different biogeographic regions. *Mar. Biol.* 155, 563-570.
- 603 Bell, J.J., Smith, D., 2004. Ecology of sponge assemblages (Porifera) in the Wakatobi
604 region, south-east Sulawesi, Indonesia: Richness and abundance. *J. Mar. Biol. Assoc.*
605 *U.K.* 84, 581-591.
- 606 Bergquist, P.R., 1965. The sponges of Micronesia, Part I: The Palau Archipelago. *Pac.*
607 *Sci.* 19, 123-204.
- 608 Bergquist, P.R., Sinclair, M.E., Hogg, J.J., 1970. Adaptation to intertidal existence:
609 reproductive cycles and larval behaviour in Demospongiae. *Symp. Zool. Soc. Lond.*
610 25, 247-271.
- 611 Bloesch, J., 1994. A review of methods used to measure sediment resuspension.
612 *Hydrobiologia* 284, 13-18.
- 613 Burnham, K.P., Anderson, D.R., 2002. *Model Selection and Multimodel Inference: A*
614 *Practical Information-Theoretic Approach*. 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag.
- 615 Butman, C.A., 1987. Larval settlement of soft-sediment invertebrates the spatial
616 scales of pattern explained by active habitat selection and the emerging role of
617 hydrodynamical processes. *Oceanography and Marine Biology an Annual Review* 25,
618 113-165.
- 619 Byers, J.E., 2002. Impact of non-indigenous species on natives enhanced by
620 anthropogenic alteration of selection regimes. *Oikos* 97, 449-458.
- 621 Carballo, J.L., 2006. Effect of natural sedimentation on the structure of tropical rocky
622 sponge assemblages. *Ecoscience* 13, 119-130.
- 623 Carballo, J.L., Nava, H., 2007. A comparison of sponge assemblage patterns in two
624 adjacent rocky habitats (tropical Pacific Ocean, Mexico). *Ecoscience* 14, 92-102.
- 625 Cheshire, A.C., Wilkinson, C.R., 1991. Modelling the photosynthetic production by
626 sponges on Davies Reef, Great Barrier Reef. *Mar. Biol.* 109, 13-18.
- 627 Chiriboga, A., Ruiz, D., Banks, S., 2011. CDF Checklist of Galapagos Sponges -
628 FCD Lista de especies de Esponjas de Galápagos, in: Bungartz, F., Herrera, H.,

- 629 Jaramillo, P., Tirado, N., Jiménez-Uzategui, G., Ruiz, D., Guézou, A. & Ziemmeck,
630 F. (Ed.), Charles Darwin Foundation Galapagos Species Checklist - Lista de Especies
631 de Galápagos de la Fundación Charles Darwin. Charles Darwin Foundation /
632 Fundación Charles Darwin, Puerto Ayora, Galapagos:
633 <http://www.darwinfoundation.org/datazone/checklists/marineinvertebrates/porifera>.
- 634 Clarke, K.R., Chapman, M.G., Somerfield, P.J., Needham, H.R., 2006a. Dispersion-
635 based weighting of species counts in assemblage analyses. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 320,
636 11-27.
- 637 Clarke, K.R., Gorley, R.N., 2006. Primer v6: User manual/tutorial. PRIMER-E Ltd:
638 Plymouth, United Kingdom.
- 639 Clarke, K.R., Somerfield, P.J., Chapman, M.G., 2006b. On resemblance measures for
640 ecological studies, including taxonomic dissimilarities and a zero-adjusted Bray-
641 Curtis coefficient for denuded assemblages. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology*
642 *and Ecology* 330, 55-80.
- 643 Cole, J.J., Findlay, S., Pace, M.L., 1988. Bacterial production in fresh and saltwater
644 ecosystems: A cross-system overview. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 43, 1-10.
- 645 Collen, J., Garton DW, Gardner JP, 2009. Shoreline Changes and Sediment
646 Redistribution at Palmyra Atoll (Equatorial Pacific Ocean): 1874-Present. *J. Coast.*
647 *Res.* 25, 711-722.
- 648 Connell, J.H., Hugues, T.P., Wallace, C.C., 1997. 30-Year study of coral abundance,
649 recruitment, and disturbance at several scales in space and time. *Ecol. Monogr.* 67,
650 461-488.
- 651 Craft, C.B., Seneca, E.D., Broome, S.W., 1991. Loss on ignition and kjeldahl
652 digestion for estimating organic-carbon and total nitrogen in estuarine marsh soils -
653 calibration with dry combustion. *Estuaries* 14, 175-179.
- 654 Cranfield, H.J., Rowden, A.A., Smith, D.J., Gordon, D.P., Michael, K.P., 2004.
655 Macrofaunal assemblages of benthic habitat of different complexity and the
656 proposition of a model of biogenic reef habitat regeneration in Foveaux Strait, New
657 Zealand. *J. Sea Res.* 52, 109-125.
- 658 Dawson, E.Y., 1959. Changes in Palmyra Atoll and its vegetation through the
659 activities of man, 1913-1958. *Pac Nat* 1, 1-52.
- 660 de Laubenfels, M.W., 1950. The sponges of Kaneohe bay, Oahu. *Pac. Sci.* 4, 3-36.
- 661 de Laubenfels, M.W., 1951. The sponges of the island of Hawaii. *Pac. Sci.* 5, 256-
662 271.
- 663 de Laubenfels, M.W., 1954. The sponges of the west central Pacific. *Oregon State*
664 *Monographs. Studies in Zoology* 7, 320.

- 665 de Voogd, N.J., Cleary, D.F.R., 2007. Relating species traits to environmental
666 variables in Indonesian coral reef sponge assemblages. *Marine and Freshwater*
667 *Research* 58, 240-249.
- 668 de Voogd, N.J., Cleary, D.F.R., Hoeksema, B.W., Noor, A., Van Soest, R.W.M.,
669 2006. Sponge beta diversity in the Spermonde Archipelago, SW Sulawesi, Indonesia.
670 *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 309, 131-142.
- 671 DeFelice, R.C., Eldredge, L.G., Carlton, J.T., 2001. Non-indigenous marine
672 invertebrates. In *A guidebook to introduced marine species in Hawai'i*, in: Eldredge,
673 L.G., Smith, C.M. (Eds.), *Bishops Museum Technical Report 21*.
- 674 Diaz, M.C., Ward, B.B., 1997. Sponge-mediated nitrification in tropical benthic
675 communities. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 156, 97-107.
- 676 Dufrene, M., Legendre, P., 1997. Species Assemblages and Indicator Species: The
677 Need for a Flexible asymmetrical approach. *Ecol. Monogr.* 67, 345-366.
- 678 Dunlap, M., Pawlik, J.R., 1996. Video-monitored predation by Caribbean reef fishes
679 on an array of mangrove and reef sponges. *Mar. Biol.* 126, 117-123.
- 680 Fabricius, K.E., 2005. Effects of terrestrial runoff on the ecology of corals and coral
681 reefs: review and synthesis. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 50, 125-146.
- 682 Folk, R.L., 1974. *Petrology of sedimentary rocks*. Hemphill Publishing Company,
683 Austin, TX, USA.
- 684 Gardner, J., Garton, D., Collen, J., 2011. Near-surface mixing and pronounced deep-
685 water stratification in a compartmentalised, human-disturbed atoll lagoon system.
686 *Coral Reefs* 30, 271-282-282.
- 687 Hodgson, G., 1990. Sediment and the settlement of larvae of the reef coral
688 *Pocillopora damicornis*. *Coral Reefs* 9, 41-43-43.
- 689 Hoegh-Guldberg, O., 2011. Coral reef ecosystems and anthropogenic climate change.
690 *Regional Environmental Change* 11, 215-227-227.
- 691 Hoover, J.P., 2006. *Hawaii's Sea Creatures, a Guide to Hawaii's Marine Invertebrates*.
692 Revised Edition. Mutual publishing.
- 693 Ilan, M., Abelson, A., 1995. The life of a sponge in a sandy lagoon. *Biological*
694 *Bulletin* 189, 363-369.
- 695 Knapp, I.S., Godwin, L.S., Smith, J.E., Williams, G.J., Bell, J.J., 2011. Records of
696 non-indigenous marine species at Palmyra Atoll in the U.S. Line Islands. *Marine*
697 *biodiversity records* 4, 1-7.
- 698 Knapp, I.S.S., Bell, J.J., 2010. Effect of depth on sponge assemblage structure at
699 Palmyra Atoll, Central Pacific. *The open marine biology journal* 4, 26-30.

- 700 Knott, N.A., Underwood, A.J., Chapman, M.G., Glasby, T.M., 2004. Epibiota on
701 vertical and on horizontal surfaces on natural reefs and on artificial structures. *J. Mar.*
702 *Biol. Assoc. U.K.* 84, 1117-1130.
- 703 Kohler, K.E., Gill, S.M., 2006. Coral Point Count with Excel extensions (CPCe): A
704 Visual Basic program for the determination of coral and substrate coverage using
705 random point count methodology. *Computers & Geosciences* 32, 1259-1269.
- 706 Lesser, M.P., 2006. Benthic-pelagic coupling on coral reefs: Feeding and growth of
707 Caribbean sponges. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol* 328, 277-288.
- 708 Maldonado, M., Young, C.M., 1996. Effects of physical factors on larval behavior,
709 settlement and recruitment of four tropical demosponges. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 138,
710 169-180.
- 711 Maragos, J.E., 1993. Impact of coastal construction on coral reefs in the United-
712 States-affiliated Pacific Islands. *Coast. Manage.* 21, 235-269.
- 713 Maragos, J.E., Williams, G.J., 2011. Pacific Coral Reefs: an introduction, in: Hopley,
714 E. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Modern Coral Reefs*. Springer-Verlag, p. 1236.
- 715 McArdle, B.H., Anderson, M.J., 2001. Fitting multivariate models to community data:
716 a comment on distance-based redundancy analysis. *Ecol. Soc.* 82, 290-297.
- 717 Moberg, F., Folke, C., 1999. Ecological goods and services of coral reef ecosystems.
718 *Ecol. Econ.* 29, 215-233.
- 719 Mooney, H.A., Cleland, E.E., 2001. The evolutionary impact of invasive species.
720 *PNAS* 98, 5446-5451.
- 721 Pawlik, J.R., 1998. Coral reef sponges: Do predatory fishes affect their distribution?
722 *Limnol. Oceanogr.* 43, 1396-1399.
- 723 Peterson, B.J., Chester, C.M., Jochem, F.J., Fourqurean, J.W., 2006. Potential role of
724 sponge communities in controlling phytoplankton blooms in Florida Bay. *Mar. Ecol.*
725 *Prog. Ser.* 328, 93-103.
- 726 Pile, A.J., Patterson, M.R., Witman, J.D., 1996. In situ grazing on plankton <10 μ m
727 by the boreal sponge *Mycale lingua*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 141, 95-102.
- 728 Powell, A.L., Hepburn, L.J., Smith, D.J., Bell, J.J., 2010. Patterns of Sponge
729 Abundance Across a Gradient of Habitat Quality in the Wakatobi Marine National
730 Park, Indonesia. *The Open Marine Biology Journal* 4, 31-38.
- 731 Rapport, D.J., Whitford, W.G., 1999. How Ecosystems Respond to Stress. *American*
732 *Institute of Biological Sciences* 49, 193-203.
- 733 Reiswig, H.M., 1971. Particle feeding in natural populations of three marine
734 demosponges. *Biological Bulletin* 141, 568-591.

- 735 Reiswig, H.M., 1975. Bacteria as food for temperate water marine sponges. *Can. J.*
736 *Zool.* 53, 582-589.
- 737 Richmond, R.H., 1993. Coral Reefs: Present Problems and Future Concerns Resulting
738 from Anthropogenic Disturbance. *Am. Zool.* 33, 524-536.
- 739 Roberts, D.E., Davis, A.R., Cummings, S.P., 2006. Experimental manipulation of
740 shade, silt, nutrients and salinity on the temperate reef sponge *Cymbastela*
741 *concentrica*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 307, 143-154.
- 742 Rogers, C.S., 1990. Responses of coral reefs and reef organisms to sedimentation.
743 *Marine Ecology-Progress Series* 62, 185-202.
- 744 Rogers, S.I., Clarke, K.R., Reynolds, J.D., 1999. The taxonomic distinctness of
745 coastal bottom-dwelling fish communities of the North-east Atlantic. *J. Anim. Ecol.*
746 68, 769-782.
- 747 Rützler, K., 1975. The role of burrowing sponges in bioerosion. *Oecologia* 19, 203-
748 216.
- 749 Soest, R.W.M.v., Kaiser, K.L., Syoc, R.v., 2011. Sponges from Clipperton Island,
750 East Pacific. *Zootaxa* 2839, 1-46.
- 751 Tyrrell, M.C., Byers, J.E., 2007. Do artificial substrates favor nonindigenous fouling
752 species over native species? *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 342, 54-60.
- 753 Vogel, S., 1977. Current-induced flow through living sponges in nature. *PNAS* 74,
754 2069-2071.
- 755 Wilkinson, C.R., 1983. Net primary productivity in coral reef sponges. *Science (U.S.)*
756 219, 410-412.
- 757 Wilkinson, C.R., Cheshire, A.C., 1988. Cross-shelf variations in coral reef structure
758 and function - influences of land and ocean. *Proceedings of the 6th international Coral*
759 *Reef Symposium* 1, 227-233.
- 760 Wilkinson, C.R., Cheshire, A.C., 1989. Patterns in the distribution of sponge
761 populations across the Central Great Barrier Reef. *Coral Reefs* 8, 127-134.
- 762 Wilkinson, C.R., Evans, E., 1989. Sponge distribution across Davies Reef, Great
763 Barrier Reef, relative to location, depth, and water movement. *Coral Reefs* 8, 1-7.
- 764 Williams, G.J., Knapp, I.S., Maragos, J.E., Davy, S.K., 2011. Proximate
765 environmental drivers of coral communities at Palmyra Atoll: establishing baselines
766 prior to removing a WWII military causeway. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.*
- 767 Woodin, S.A., 1986. Settlement of infauna: larval choice? *Bull. Mar. Sci.* 39, 401-
768 407.

- 769 Wulff, J.L., 1984. Sponge-mediated coral reef growth and rejuvenation. *Coral Reefs*
770 3, 157-163.
- 771 Wulff, J.L., 1994. Sponge feeding by Caribbean angelfishes, trunkfishes, and
772 filefishes, in: Soest, R.W.M.v., van Kempen, T.G., Braekman, J.C. (Eds.), *Sponge in*
773 *time and space; Biology, Chemistry, Paleontology*. A.A. Balkema, Rotterdam, pp.
774 265-271.
- 775 Wulff, J.L., 2000. Sponge predators may determine differences in sponge fauna
776 between two sets of mangrove cays, Belize Barrier Reef. *Atoll Res. Bull.*, 251-263.
- 777 Wulff, J.L., 2001. Assessing and monitoring coral reef sponges: Why and how? *Bull.*
778 *Mar. Sci.* 69, 831-846.
- 779 Zea, S., 1994. Patterns of coral and sponge abundance in stressed coral reefs at Santa
780 Marta, Colombian Caribbean, in: Soest, R.W.M.v., van Kempen, T.G., Braekman,
781 J.C. (Eds.), *Sponge in time and space; Biology, Chemistry, Paleontology*. A.A.
782 Balkema, Rotterdam, pp. 257-264.
783

Figures and tables (colour version below)

Figure 1. Map indicating the location of Palmyra Atoll, within the Central Pacific and the 11 survey sites within the 4 lagoons: Sand Island (Sa); Strawn Island (St); Ripple wharf (Rw); Paradise Island (P); the Dolphins (D); the Cut (C); South of the Cut (S.C); Quail Island (Q); Eastern Island (E.I); Central Eastern (C.E); Turtle pool (TP) across the 4 lagoons. The black arrows indicate locations of military modifications; 1= the western boat channel, 2= the airstrip made of dredge spoil and coral rubble and 3= the north-south causeway, specifically the cut allowing boat access between the Central and Eastern lagoons.

Figure 2. Measures of overall % cover, number of species, Hills N1, N2 and N21' across all sites (means \pm SD). Lagoons are indicated as W= Western, C= Central, E= Eastern and TP= Turtle Pool.

Figure 3. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) bi-plot ordination showing the indicator sponge species across sites and lagoon. Based upon a zero-adjusted Bray-Curtis similarity matrix with a dispersion weighting pretreatment on sponge area cover data, which are pre-adjusted to the amount of available substrate. The analyses were based on 9999 random permutations. A Pearson's correlation coefficient of ≥ 0.5 was used to indicate these vectors.

Figure 4. Ranked abundances of sponge species in the lagoons at Palmyra. Bars are stacked and indicate the mean average per lagoon, but not the total mean across all lagoons where W= Western, C= Central, E= Eastern and TP= Turtle Pool. (★) marks the indicator species as indicated in **Figure 3**.

Figure 5. Distance-based redundancy analysis (dbRDA) visualising the similarity in sponge assemblages and the correlated change in environmental conditions among the 11 lagoon sites (**Fig 1**) for both mean percentage area cover (top) and sponge assemblages (bottom).

Figure 6. Underwater photos of Palmyra reef, lagoon and sponges. A) Current day conditions in the lagoon versus the reef. B) Examples of the military modifications; debris left in the lagoon, the Ripple wharf covered in fouling organisms, and a diver with survey quadrat and an example of the dolphin structures behind. C) Sponges and sediment; different strategies to deal sedimentation. From left to right: *Iotrochota protea* (U), no sediment on oscular or veins; *Dysidea sp2* (C), sediment accumulates primarily on the protruding spikes, raised oscular; *Spirastrella* sp. (E), extended oscular. All letters in brackets relate to the species ID in **Table 1**.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Table 1. List of species found within the lagoons at Palmyra Atoll. A-X samples are those species found within the quadrats. AA-AL are those species found outside the quadrats or excavating species.

ID List	Genus	Family	Suborder	Order	Reference
A cf. <i>Aplysilla rosea</i>	<i>Aplysilla</i>	Darwinellidae	n/a	Dendroceratida	Barrois, 1876
B <i>Dysidea</i> sp.1	<i>Dysidea</i> sp.1	Dysideidae	n/a	Dictyoceratida	Johnston, 1842
C <i>Dysidea</i> sp.2 cf. <i>etherea</i>	<i>Dysidea</i> sp.2	Dysideidae	n/a	Dictyoceratida	Johnston, 1842
D <i>Spirastrella</i> sp.	<i>Spirastrella</i> sp.	Spirastrellidae	n/a	Hadromerida	Schmidt, 1868
E <i>Scopalina</i> sp.	<i>Scopalina</i> sp.	Dictyonellidae	n/a	Halichondrida	Schmidt, 1862
F <i>Halichondria</i> sp.1	<i>Halichondria</i> sp.1	Halichondriidae	n/a	Halichondrida	Fleming, 1828
G <i>Halichondria</i> sp.2	<i>Halichondria</i> sp.2	Halichondriidae	n/a	Halichondrida	Fleming, 1828
H <i>Hymeniacion</i> sp.1	<i>Hymeniacion</i> sp.1	Halichondriidae	n/a	Halichondrida	Bowerbank, 1858
I <i>Halichondriidae</i> sp.1	unknown	Halichondriidae sp.1	n/a	Halichondrida	Gray, 1867
J <i>Halichondriidae</i> sp.2	unknown	Halichondriidae sp.2	n/a	Halichondrida	Bowerbank, 1858
K <i>Chalinula</i> sp.	<i>Chalinula</i> sp.	Chalinidae	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Schmidt, 1868
L <i>Haliclona</i> (<i>Sigmatocia</i>) <i>caerulea</i>	<i>Haliclona</i>	Chalinidae	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Hechtel, 1965
M <i>Haliclona</i> sp.1	<i>Haliclona</i> sp.1	Chalinidae	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Grant, 1836
N Challyspongiidae sp.	unknown	Challyspongiidae sp.	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	de Laubenfels, 1936
O <i>Gelliodes fibrosa</i>	<i>Gelliodes</i>	Niphatidae	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Wilson, 1925
P Niphatidae sp.1	unknown	Niphatidae sp.1	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Van Soest, 1980
Q Haplosclerida sp.	unknown	unknown	unknown	Haplosclerida sp.	Topsent, 1928
R <i>Acarinus</i> sp.1	<i>Acarinus</i> sp.1	Acarinidae	Microcionina	Poecilosclerida	Gray, 1867
S <i>Acarinus</i> sp.2	<i>Acarinus</i> sp.2	Acarinidae	Microcionina	Poecilosclerida	Gray, 1867
T Chondropsidae sp.	unknown	Chondropsidae sp.	Myxillina	Poecilosclerida	Carter, 1886
U <i>Iatrochota protea</i>	<i>Iatrochota</i>	Iatrochotidae	Myxillina	Poecilosclerida	Ridley, 1884
V Iatrochotidae sp.	unknown	Iatrochotidae sp.	Myxillina	Poecilosclerida	Dendy, 1922
W <i>Clathria</i> sp.	<i>Clathria</i> sp.	Microcionidae	Microcionina	Poecilosclerida	Schmidt, 1862
X <i>Hexadella</i> sp.	<i>Hexadella</i> sp.	Ianthellidae	n/a	Verongida	Topsent, 1896
AA Darwinellidae sp.	unknown	unknown	Darwinellidae sp.	Dendroceratida	Merejkowsky, 1879
AB <i>Cliona</i> sp.1	<i>Cliona</i> sp.1	Clionidae	n/a	Hadromerida	Grant, 1826
AC <i>Cliona</i> sp.2	<i>Cliona</i> sp.2	Clionidae	n/a	Hadromerida	Grant, 1826
AD Suberitidae sp.1	unknown	Suberitidae sp.1	n/a	Hadromerida	Schmidt, 1870
AE Suberitidae sp.2	unknown	Suberitidae sp.2	n/a	Hadromerida	Schmidt, 1870
AF <i>Hymeniacion</i> sp.	<i>Hymeniacion</i> sp.	Halichondriidae	n/a	Halichondrida	Bowerbank, 1858
AG Halichondriidae sp.3	unknown	Halichondriidae sp.	n/a	Halichondrida	Bowerbank, 1858
AH <i>Haliclona</i> sp.2	<i>Haliclona</i> sp.2	Chalinidae	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Grant, 1836
AI Niphatidae sp.2	unknown	Niphatidae sp.2	Haplosclerina	Haplosclerida	Van Soest, 1980
AJ Microcionidae sp.	unknown	Microcionidae sp.	Microcionina	Poecilosclerida	Carter, 1875
AK Myxillidae sp.	unknown	Myxillidae sp.	Myxillina	Poecilosclerida	Dendy, 1922
AL Poecilosclerida sp.	unknown	unknown	unknown	Poecilosclerida sp.	Topsent, 1928

Table 2. Results from CAP analyses examining sponge assemblage variability in cover between sites and lagoons. Sa, Sand Island; St, Strawn Island; Rw, Ripple wharf; P, Paradise Island; D, the dolphins; C, the cut; S.C, south of the cut; Q, Quail Island; E.I, Eastern Island; C.E, Central Eastern; TP, Turtle pool; W, Western lagoon; C, Central lagoon; E, Eastern lagoon; TP, Turtle pool. Where *m* is the number of principal coordinate (PCO) axes used in the analyses, % Var the percentage of the total variation explained by the first *m* PCO axes, δ^2 the squared canonical correlation and allocation success values the percentage of samples correctly allocated into their corresponding groups using the first *m* PCO axes from the model.

Factor	<i>m</i>	% Var	δ^2	P
Site	7	76.6	0.82	0.0001
Lagoon	9	86.0	0.75	0.0001

Allocation success											
Site	Sa	St	Rw	P	D	C	S.C	Q	E.I	C.E	TP
	50	40	90	50	60	70	60	40	60	60	70

Lagoon	W	C	E	TP
	90	65	80	70

Table 4. Results of the distance-based permutational multiple regression analysis (DISTLM) for overall mean % cover, sponge species assemblage and the introduced and potentially introduced species. Only the optimal variables of spatial change in sponge assemblages are shown along with the proportion of variability they explain. Model selection was based on Akaike's Information Criterion with a second-order bias correction applied (AICc), with the total variation explained (r^2) by each best-fit model shown (% total) based on 9999 random permutations of the raw data. Variables were normalized and fitted in a step-wise manner.

Model	AICc	Predictor	Pseudo-F	P	%Var
Mean % cover	54.44	Turb	5.95	0.0317	39.79
		Flow_1SD	4.53	0.0497	21.78
		Hard_cov	6.69	0.0305	18.78
		Total			80.35
Sponge assemblages	801.51	Angle	8.21	0.0001	7.07
		Chl- <i>a</i> _1SD	7.96	0.0001	6.11
		Mil_cov	6.65	0.0001	5.44
		Hard_cov	7.57	0.0001	4.55
		Turb	5.56	0.0001	4.09
		Temp	5.35	0.0001	3.78
		PCOM	5.02	0.0001	3.34
		Soft_cov	5.13	0.0001	3.28
		M.algae	3.25	0.0018	2.25
		Total			39.91
<i>Haliclona caerulea</i>	87.58	Temp	3.03	0.0529	25.25
<i>Gelliodes fibrosa</i>	86.08	PCOM	3.68	0.0568	29.03
<i>Iotrochota protea</i>	72.52	Angle	3.54	0.1104	28.24
		Chl- <i>a</i> _1SD	6.89	0.0176	33.20
		Total			61.43

Figures and table in colour

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

